

FORENSIC SCIENCE EDUCATION AND LAW OF EVIDENCE SUBJECT: ITS CONNECTION AND IMPORTANT

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Abstract

The use of forensic science has become very important in today's world particularly in the case of investigation and prosecution of crime. Due to its important, forensic science has become important tool to prove or disprove certain fact and fact in issue in the court of law. Forensic science has now become part and parcel of evidence. The terms forensic science and evidence have becoming synonym to each other. Since they are inseparable, the topic of forensic science becoming important component for law of evidence subject which been offered for law programme by law school in colleges and universities in many countries including in Malaysia. What is forensic science? Forensic science is the use of science to investigate a case in order to present unbiased scientific evidence that can be presented in court. Forensic science, also known is the application of science principles and methods to support legal decision-making in matters of criminal and civil law. During investigation, it is governed by the legal standards of admissible evidence and procedural process. It is a broad field utilizing numerous practices such as the analysis of DNA, fingerprints, bloodstain patterns, firearms, ballistics, toxicology, microscopy and fire debris analysis. Due to its complexity, not everybody can perform the duty and responsibility to collect forensic evidence. Any small mistake can spoil the forensic evidence and make such forensic evidence inadmissible by the court. Crucial to note, the submission of evidence in Malaysian court is heavily regulated by the evidence statutes. For civil courts, it is regulated by the Evidence Act 1950 [Act 56] and for the Syariah court, it is regulated by the states respective Syariah Evidence Enactments or Acts. All these statutes provide strict conditions for the admissibility of evidence. Only relevant, strong, and convincing evidence can be admissible by the court. The submission of evidences will also need to fulfil the quantum of proof provided for the case. Basically, there are two sets of standard or quantum of proof which need to be satisfied before the defendant or accused can be found guilty and faced legal sentence namely balance of probabilities which been adopted in civil trial and beyond a reasonable doubt for criminal trial. As such, only those who has been properly trained and equipped with forensic science knowledge are allowed to perform such duty and responsibility does handle forensic evidence. These people are generally known as forensic scientist. Forensic scientists will collect, preserve, and analyze evidence during the course of an investigation. Some forensic scientists travel to the scene of the crime to collect the evidence themselves, others occupy a laboratory role, performing analysis on objects brought to them by other individuals. Others are involved in analysis of financial, banking, or other numerical data for use in financial crime investigation, and can be employed as consultants from private firms, academia, or as government employees. In addition to their laboratory role, forensic scientists testify as expert witnesses in both criminal and civil cases and can work for either the prosecution or the defense. Thus, it is the object of this research to analyses deeper over forensic science education as well as its connection and important to the law of evidence subject offered by law school.

Keywords: Forensic, Science, Education, Evidence, Law

1.0 INTRODUCTION

We are living in a world where crimes become rampant. Every day, we have to listen to the reported news over crimes committed against person, property and environment. With the increasing number of crimes, new method of proof is needed in order to bring a successful case against the perpetrator, protect the right of the victim, to uphold justice and to maintain social order. We simply cannot rely wholly on the limited provisions of the existing statutes in order to protect the interest of everyone or everything. Because of this the law has developed forensic science in order to assist the enforcement agencies to enforce all the existing laws. Forensic science is an important feature of the criminal justice system in many countries including in Malaysia. Forensic science deals with exploring the scientific and physical clues collected from the crime scene. Forensic science describes the suspect's distinctive nature which committed the crime. The evidence clearly points out the essence of the crime that was committed. The circumstantial evidence even refers to the time of the occurrence. The forensic evidence indicates where the crime is located. The forensic investigation even follows the offender's process. Finally, the motive behind the crime comes to a close. Forensic analysts recreate the peculiarity of the suspect and the victim. In investigating a criminal act, a large array of forensic science and forensic resources are involved. During the entire criminal investigation, the evidence is collected from the scene of the crime or by a person who is an eye witness to the complete event, which is further analyzed in a forensic lab and then the findings are reported to the judge. Every crime investigation is unique in nature and poses its own challenges in each instance. Forensic science plays a significant role in the criminal justice system by offering scientifically based knowledge through the study of the physical proof, the identification of the perpetrator by personal clues such as fingerprints, footprints, blood drops or ears, cell phones or any other devices, automobiles and arms. Thus, it will be very difficult for any enforcement agencies to carry out their enforcement duties and responsibilities without the aid from forensic science. Whether we like it or not, forensic science has now become part and parcel of our daily life. Forensic science is here to stay and to be strengthening from time to time in line with the advancement of science and technology. As we give our so much focus to Artificial Intelligence or AI, we also must not forget to give our focus to forensic science.

When it all started? It is hard to identify the exact time over the use of forensic science from recorded history. The ancient world lacked standardized forensic practices, which enabled criminals to escape punishment. Criminal investigations and trials relied heavily on forced confessions and witness testimony. However, ancient sources do contain several accounts of techniques that foreshadow concepts in forensic science developed centuries later (Schafer, Elizabeth D., 2008). The first written account of using medicine and entomology to solve criminal cases is attributed to the book of Xi Yuan Lu (translated as Washing Away of Wrongs), written in China in 1248 by Song Ci (1186–1249), a director of justice, jail and supervision, during the Song dynasty period (Song Ci, 1981). Song Ci introduced regulations concerning autopsy reports to court, how to protect the evidence in the examining process, and explained why forensic workers must demonstrate impartiality to the public. He devised methods for making antiseptic and for promoting the reappearance of hidden injuries to dead bodies and bones (using sunlight and vinegar under a red-oil umbrella); for calculating the time of death (allowing for weather and insect activity); described how to wash and examine the dead body to ascertain the reason for death. At that time the book had described methods for distinguishing between suicide and faked suicide. He wrote the book on forensics stating that all wounds or dead bodies should be examined, not avoided. The book became the first form of literature to help determine the cause of death (Iorliam, Aamo, 2018). In one of Song Ci's accounts (Washing Away of Wrongs), the case of a person murdered with a sickle was solved by an investigator who instructed each suspect to bring his sickle to one location. (He realized it was a sickle by testing various blades on an animal carcass and comparing the wounds.) Flies, attracted by the smell of blood, eventually gathered on a single sickle. In light of this, the owner of that sickle confessed to the murder. The book also described how to distinguish between a drowning (water in the lungs) and strangulation (broken neck cartilage), and described evidence from examining corpses to determine if a death was caused by murder, suicide or accident. Methods from around the world involved saliva and examination of the mouth and tongue to determine innocence or guilt, as a precursor to the Polygraph test.

In Islam, the concept of forensic science has been given an emphasized under the Islamic legal principle. In Islamic judicial process, the law of evidence is very important because the judge need to decide any case put forward to him based on the evidence/s presented. The quality of evidence/s collected and presented to the judge is extremely high in order to ensure justice and fairness. Allah SWT also commands the believer to

judge between people with justice and fairness. This has been mentioned many times in the Holy Qur'an. The Holy Qur'an says in Surah al-Nisa verse 58, which means: "Allah doth command you to render back your trusts to those to whom they are due, and when ye judge between man and man, that ye judge with justice, verily how excellent is the teaching which He giveth you!". The Holy Qur'an says in Surah al-Ma'idah, verse 42, which means: "If thou judge, judge in equity between them, for Allah loveth those who judge in equity". In verse 49 of Surah al-Ma'idah, the Holy Qur'an says, which means: "And this (He commands): judge thou between them by what God hath revealed, and follow not their vain desires, but beware lest they beguile thee from any of that (teaching) which God hath sent down to thee". The Holy Qur'an says in Surah al-Nisa', verse 105 which means: "We have sent down to thee the Book in truth, that thou might judge between men, as guided by Allah, so be not (used) as an advocate by those who betray their trust". The Holy Qur'an says in Surah al-Ma'idah, verse 8 which means: "O ye who believe! Stand out firmly for Allah, as witnesses to fair dealing, and let not the hatred of others to you make you swerve to wrong and depart from justice. Be just, that is next to piety". The Holy Qur'an says in Surah al-Nisa', verse 135 which means: "O ye who believe! Stand out firmly for justice, as witnesses to God, even as against yourselves, or your parents, or your kin, and whether it be (against) rich or poor, for God can best protect both. Follow not the lusts (of your hearts), lest ye swerve, and if ye distort (justice) or decline to do justice". The Holy Qur'an says in Surah al-Baqarah, verse 283 which means: "Conceal not evidence, for whoever conceals it, his heart is tainted with sin". The Holy Qur'an says in Surah al-Baqarah, verse 282 which means: "The witnesses should not refuse when they are called on (for evidence)". These mentioned verses are only part of many authorities which been provided in the Holy Qur'an and the practice of the Holy Prophet Muhammad SAW which demands the submission and present of evidence when judging any dispute. Such evidences include documentary evidence (Al – Kitabah), testimony of a witness (Shahadah), opinion by an expert witness (Ray Al – Khabir) and many more. Islamic law of evidence does not prohibit or bar the use of forensic science as part of evidence. There are many Syariah Court cases which allow the use of forensic science evidence like Sabah State Syarie Prosecutor v Rosli Abdul Japar [2007] 1 CLJ SYA 496, Eddyham bin Zainuddin v Rahimah binti Muhamad (05000-006- 0011-2012), Mohd Zulhaini Uzir v Fadzlina Mohd Fadzil [2012] 1 CLJ (SYA), Zakaria@Supar bin Ali v Haznah@Maznah binti Embong [2012] 2 ShLR 12. Thus, it can be concluded that forensic science evidence has been accepted by judges in the Malaysian Syariah Courts to resolve certain cases, as demonstrated in the above reported and unreported court cases. Case analysis shows that forensic science evidence can be accepted in Islamic evidence law as a form of evidence to establish facts and to uphold justice and fairness.

2.0 FORENSIC SCIENCE

Before we go further, it is very important for us to closely examine the meaning of forensic science itself first. What is forensic science? Forensic science, also known as criminalistics, is the application of science principles and methods to support legal decision-making in matters of criminal and civil law. The term criminalistic is difference from criminology. Criminology is the study of crime and its prevention, as well as the exploration of criminals and their treatment. This type of study is available at both the bachelor's and master's degree levels. Criminology students study the criminal justice system and develop new theories for dealing with crime and its causes. Typical course topics in a criminology program include deviance, juvenile delinquency, punishment, criminological theory, and social research. Meanwhile, criminalistics, also known as forensic science, is the application of scientific principles to provide evidence in criminal cases. Students can earn either a bachelor's or master's degree in this field. Trained physicians also study the topic within fellowship programs in forensic pathology. Students in forensic science programs learn how to collect crime scene evidence, prove the causes of accidents, and test crime scene evidence in labs. General course topics include crime scene investigation, drug analysis, genetics, physics, organic chemistry, criminal procedures, and the criminal justice system (Best Accredited Colleges, 2024).

Come back to the concept of forensic science, it is a broad field utilizing numerous practices such as the analysis of Deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA), fingerprints, bloodstain patterns, firearms, ballistics, toxicology, microscopy, fire debris analysis and many more. The task to collect such scientific evidence cannot be given to anyone. Only those who are qualified and properly trained can collect the such scientific evidence and present it to the court for legal proceeding. Those people are mostly known as forensic scientist. Forensic scientists collect, preserve, and analyze evidence during the course of an investigation. While some forensic scientists travel to the scene of the crime to collect the evidence themselves, others occupy a laboratory role, performing analysis on objects brought to them by other individuals (Crime Scene Investigator Edu.Org, 2024). A forensic science job description may appear distinctly different depending on the area of forensic

science being practiced. This is because forensic science is a rather broad field and thus encompasses a number of specialties, all of which are rooted in the natural sciences. Forensic science work generally involves one or more areas of science: Chemistry: Involves the study of paint, chemicals, and similar substances and compounds, Biology: Involves trace and DNA evidence, including blood, hair, fibers, etc and Drugs/toxicology: Involves testing for the presence or absence of drugs, alcohol and poisons in blood, urine, and tissues samples. It may also involve specific subspecialties of forensic science, such as botany, anthropology, and odontology (dentistry). A forensic scientist may therefore take on one or more of the following forensic science jobs namely criminalist, forensic toxicologist, forensic pathologist, forensic anthropologist, forensic odontologist, forensic botanist, forensic biologist, forensic chemist, documents examiner, fingerprint examiner, DNA analyst, trace evidence analyst, medical examiner and others. The job duties of a forensic scientist may vary according to the field of interest or specialty, but they all have one thing in common: they identify and interpret physical evidence collected from a crime scene. Forensic scientists generally perform their work inside the forensic or crime laboratory, where they are responsible for comparing and interpreting the physical evidence that was retrieved by crime scene investigators at the scene of the crime. In specific circumstances, forensic scientists may be required at the scene of a crime, usually when the methods or techniques surrounding the collection or preservation of the physical evidence are in question. Common responsibilities of forensic scientists include carrying out laboratory examinations and analyses submitted by law enforcement agencies and medical examiners, serving as expert witnesses in a court of law, carrying out tests using scientific techniques, such as infrared spectroscopy, mass spectrometry, and scanning electron microscopy, ensuring all laboratory protocols and regulations are followed, inputting data into computer programs and utilizing relevant computer database information, overseeing the maintenance and calibration of laboratory equipment, preparing written reports based on evidence analysis, coordinating the activities related to crime scene collection, preservation, and transportation, serving as a liaison between the forensic laboratory and crime scene investigators, developing, maintaining and updating work quality standards, standard operating procedures, and similar methods and procedures, coordinating work with other members of the forensic team and with outside agencies.

Every country which provide forensic science within their justice system has their own specialize department or agency to conduct the forensic investigation. In Malaysia, there are various departments and agencies which provide services on such matter. Such departments or agencies can fall under public or private sector. However, the most notable department or agency in the country is the Department of Chemistry, Malaysia or also known in Malay as Jabatan Kimia Malaysia or KIMIA Malaysia. This department is a government department provided under the Ministry of Science, Technology and Innovation (MOSTI). The department has long historical record of existence in the country which going back to the British Colonial period in Malaysia. This department is made up of laboratory network throughout the country, providing scientific analysis, investigation and consultancy to government agencies. It aims to support law enforcement together with the implementation of programmes related to water safety, food, environment and industrial products to protect and develop public health and safety to the public, and protect the interests of consumers as well as health and safety at the workplace. The department also provides technical and consultancy services in valuation of product specifications for government contracts, to ensure the value of government expenditure, customs Tariff classification article for import/export and for the purpose of leasehold collection and to ensure the government's revenue and evaluation of chemical laboratorium for compliance with the International Organization for Standardization (ISO) standards. Food and several industrial products for export are also analyzed to ensure adherence to quality standards and international safety and thus ensure competitiveness in the global market. The provision of this service is available throughout the country including the laboratories located at the headquarters in Petaling Jaya along with 13 other strategic locations in Alor Setar, Pulau Pinang, Ipoh, Melaka, Kota Bharu, Kuala Terengganu, Kuantan, Johor Bahru, Kota Kinabalu, Tawau, Kuching, Sibul and Bintulu.

The department also provide the Forensic Science Analysis Centre which is the most important centre analysing forensic matters. It is a nationally recognized leader in the forensic science community, provides independent and impartial forensic science services to both government agencies and to the private sector. In the Forensic Science Analysis Centre, there are several Divisions namely Narcotics Division, Toxicology Division., Forensic DNA Division., Criminalistics Division as well as Document Examination Division. These services are available in the Headquarters and all the State/Branch Laboratories of Kimia Malaysia, except for : DNA analysis is available in the Headquarters Petaling Jaya, Johor State Laboratory, Penang State Laboratory, Sarawak State Laboratory and Sabah State Laboratory and Document Examination services are

available in the Headquarters Petaling Jaya, Sabah State Laboratory and Penang State Laboratory. In addition to the above, the center also provides other scientific support services including, expert opinions, lectures and training to law enforcement agencies, the Attorney General's Chambers (AGC), fellows under the United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC) training program and undergraduates or postgraduates of forensic science courses overseas scientist (Department of Chemistry, Malaysia, 2024).

3.0 FORENSIC SCIENCE EDUCATION AND LAW OF EVIDENCE SUBJECT: ITS CONNECTION AND IMPORTANCE

Forensic science and law of evidence subject which been offered by many law schools is inseparable. Both connected to each other. Law of evidence is the subject which studies the method of proof. Meanwhile, forensic science is one of the methods of proof. Forensic science education strengthens the law of evidence subject. Without forensic science education, law of evidence subject becomes pointless. We need to accept the fact that forensic science education is important subject which need to be included under the law of evidence subject and be teach to the law students. Law students need to be equipped with the basic information's pertaining to the forensic science education in order to enhance their legal capability once they enter into the legal profession. Malaysia is lucky because many of its law have been codified into a statute or written laws. As such, it is to identify the existing laws and make necessary amendment to strengthen such laws in line with many changes in today world and this include the area involving forensic science. Before going further, let us examine the basic structure of the Malaysia legal system first. The law of Malaysia is mainly based on the common law legal system. This was a direct result of the colonization of Malaya (Peninsular Malaysia), Sarawak, and North Borneo (Now Sabah) by Britain between the early 19th century to the 1960s. (Wu Min Aun, 1997, pp: 1 – 41). The supreme law of the land is the Federal Constitution. As the highest law in the country, the Federal Constitution sets out the legal framework and rights of Malaysian citizens. There are basically three sources of Malaysian law namely written law, unwritten law and Muslim law. (Lee Mei Pheng, 1997, pp: 13 – 47). There are several laws which operate in the country. Federal laws enacted by the Parliament of Malaysia apply throughout the country. There are also state laws enacted by the State Legislative Assemblies which applies in the particular state. The Federal Constitution also provides for a unique dual justice system namely the man-made laws (criminal and civil) and Syariah laws. Due to these unique dual justice systems, the county also has two set of judicial avenues namely the Civil Court and the Syariah Court, unlike Saudi Arabia which effectively equates Syariah law to national law, Malaysia only partially implements the system. Syariah law in Malaysia applies only to restricted areas of personal and family law, such as marriage and custody-and only to Muslims. Article 121 (1A) of the Federal Constitution gives exclusive jurisdiction to the Syariah Courts in the administration of Islamic laws. (Ashgar Ali Ali Mohamed (Ed.), 2014, pp: 319 – 349). However, despite having Islam as its official religion, Malaysia is not strictly an Islamic state as it allows other religions to be practiced within it in peace and harmony. Most of the Malaysian law is a man-made or secular civil law derived from the British common law system. Often, English legislation and case law still apply, as legacies of colonialism that remain in many former British colonies. (Victoria Soh, 2020). The application of English law or common law is specified in statutes. Section 5 of Criminal Procedure Code [Act 593] states that English law shall be applied in cases where no specific legislation has been enacted. Similarly, in context of civil law, Sections 3 and 5 of Civil Law Act [Act 67] allows for application of English common law, equity rules, and statutes in Malaysian civil cases where no specific laws have been made.

The effect of having these unique dual justice systems can also be seen in the evidence matter. As for civil court, the submission of evidence is regulated under the Evidence Act 1950 [Act 56]. Section 2 of Evidence Act 1950 [Act 56] states that "This Act shall apply to all judicial proceedings in or before any court, but not to affidavits presented to any court or officers, nor to proceedings before an arbitrator". This means that Evidence Act 1950 [Act 56] regulates the submission of evidence for civil and criminal proceeding in the country. Reference can be made to the following case of *Saminathan v PP* [1955] MLJ 121, *Re Loh Kah Kheng* (1990) 2 MLJ 126, *Malaysia Building Society Bhd v Univein Sdn Bhd* [2003] 5 MLJ 394, *Far East Holdings Bhd & Anor v Majlis Ugama Islam and Adat Resam Melayu Pahang and other appeals* [2018] 1 MLJ 1 and many more. The word "court" under Section 2 of the Evidence Act 1950 [Act 56] means a court established by or under Part IX of the Federal Constitution which includes a judge, a Sessions Court judge, a Magistrate, and every person legally authorized to take evidence (Except for arbitrator). Evidence Act 1950 [Act 56] does not apply to Domestic Inquiry, Tribunals, Industrial Court and Syariah Court. Examples of Tribunals include Tribunal for Consumer Claims, Tribunal for Homebuyers Claims, and Copyright Tribunal. The exclusion of the Evidence Act 1950 [Act 56] from the Syariah Court can also be seen under Section 131

of the Syariah Court Evidence Act (FT) 1997 [Act 561] which clearly states “With the coming into operation of this Act (i.e The Syariah Court Evidence Act), the Evidence Act 1950 [Act 56] shall not be applicable to the Court. (i.e. Syariah Court)”. The Malaysian Evidence Act 1950 [Act 56] is modeled and based on the Indian Evidence Act of 1872 [Act No. 1 of 1872] drafted by Sir James Stephen. The Malaysian Evidence Act 1950 [Act 56] is modeled on the Indian Evidence Act which is a codified form of English Law. Per Thomson CJ (as he then was) in *Looi Wooi Saik v PP* [1962] MLJ 337, 339 (CA) stated “In this country the question is governed by the terms of the Evidence Ordinance which is the same as the Indian Evidence Act...It is generally accepted that the Indian Act was drafted by Sir James Stephen in 1872 with the intention of stating in a codified form of English law relating to evidence as it stood at that date”. The Indian Evidence Act 1872 [Act No. 1 of 1872] which also is based on the English law of evidence in the late 19TH century with certain modifications, which were made to suit the local circumstances in India. As result of several amendments, the local Malaysian Evidence Act 1950 [Act 56] has certain provisions which are not found in the Indian Evidence Act 1872 [Act No. 1 of 1872]. The Malaysian Evidence Act 1950 [Act 56] has 167 sections which covered various aspect over submission of evidence in the Malaysian court. Generally, the Malaysian Evidence Act 1950 [Act 56] embodied aspects over the definition of evidence, types of evidence and the method of authentication of evidence. (Augustine Paul, 2000, pp. 1 – 13).

There are many provisions inside the Evidence Act 1950 [Act 56] which need the aid for forensic science for instant Section 7, 8 and 9 of the Evidence Act 1950 [Act 56] which provide for circumstantial evidences like finger print, footprint, as well as identification and DNA evidence. All these evidences need forensic science to examine the genuineness before it to be declaring legally admissible and to be accepted by the court of law. The submission of documentary evidence also relies heavily on forensic science. The area of documentary evidence is very wide and it can include anything beside a piece of paper. This can be seen over the definition of document itself which been provided under Section 3 of the Evidence Act 1950 [Act 56]. Its states “document” means any matter expressed, described, or howsoever represented, upon any substance, material, thing or article, including any matter embodied in a disc, tape, film, sound-track or other device whatsoever, by means of (a) letters, figures, marks, symbols, signals, signs, or other forms of expression, description, or representation whatsoever; (b) any visual recording (whether of still or moving images); (c) any sound recording, or any electronic, magnetic, mechanical or other recording whatsoever and howsoever made, or any sounds, electronic impulses, or other data whatsoever; (d) a recording, or transmission, over a distance of any matter by any, or any combination, of the means mentioned in paragraph (a), (b) or (c), or by more than one of the means mentioned in paragraphs (a), (b), (c) and (d), intended to be used or which may be used for the purpose of expressing, describing, or howsoever representing, that matter. The submission of a paper, ancient document, computer generated document, tape recorder, smart phone or any modern materials which can be associate with document which need the assistance of forensic science for its authentication process.

The discussion over forensic science also relates to the area of expert witness. As mentioned earlier in this research, not everyone can do the necessary collection and examination of forensic evidence. It can only be done by those who are qualified in the area of forensic science in order to ensure the reliability of the submitted evidence to the court of law. Section 45 of the Evidence Act 1950 [Act 56] allow the submission of testimony by expert witness. Such expert witness included the forensic scientist. Who is an expert witness? An expert witness is a witness, who by virtue of education, training, skill, or even experience, is believed to have sufficient knowledge in a particular area of interest or subject beyond that of the average person, sufficient that others may officially (and legally) rely upon the witness’s specialized opinion about an evidence or fact issue within the scope of their expertise, referred to as the expert opinion, as an assistance to the fact-finder. Section 45 of the Evidence Act 1950 [Act 56] provides the opinions of experts. It states when the court has to form an opinion upon a point of foreign law or of science or art, or as to identity or genuineness of handwriting or finger impressions, the opinions upon that point of persons specially skilled in that foreign law, science or art, or in questions as to identity or genuineness of handwriting or finger impressions, are relevant facts. (2) Such persons are called experts. An expert witness is required when it is necessary to have opinion evidence to assist in the resolution of a dispute. This opinion may lead to an early resolution of the dispute. An expert witness may be involved in court proceedings and may be called to give evidence. Reference can be made to the case of *Mohamad Shariff Abu Hassan v Lee Kok Chung* [2021] 1 LNS 1932. Per Abdul Hamid FJ in *Syed Abu Bakar Bin Ahmad v PP* [1984] 2 MLJ 19 states “There are however cases in which the Court is not in a position to form a correct judgment without help of persons who have acquired special skill or experience on a particular subject, e.g. when the question involved is beyond the range of common experience or common knowledge or when special study of a subject or special

training or special experience therein is necessary. In such cases the help of experts is required. In these cases, the rule is relaxed and expert evidence is admitted to enable the court to come to a proper decision". In *Wong Swee Chin v PP* [1977] 1 LNS 156 where Azlan Shah CJ (as he then was) delivering the judgment of the Court explained who are experts in, and then went on to say: "Our system of jurisprudence does not, generally speaking, remit the determination of dispute to experts. Some questions are left to the robust good sense of a jury. Others are resolved by the conventional wisdom of a Judge sitting alone. In the course of elucidating disputed questions, aids in the form of expert opinions are in appropriate cases placed before juries or Judges. But, except on purely scientific issues, expert evidence is to be used by the Court for the purpose of assisting rather than compelling the formulation of the ultimate judgments...". The competency of an expert is determined by the court itself. Reference can be made to the following cases like *Herchun Singh & Ors v Public Prosecutor* [1969] 1 LNS 52; [1969] 2 MLJ 209 FC, *Dato' Mokhtar Hashim & Anor v Public Prosecutor* [1983] CLJ (Rep) 101 FC; [1983] 2 CLJ 10; *Lai Kim Hon & Ors v Public Prosecutor* [1980] 1 LNS 197; [1981] 1 MLJ 84 FC, *Che Omar bin Mohd Akhir v Public Prosecutor* [1999] 2 CLJ 780 CA, *Public Prosecutor v Mohd Radzi Abu Bakar* [2006] 1 CLJ 457 FC); [2005] 6 MLJ 393; [2005] 6 AMR 203, *Lee Gee Hian v PP* [2021] 1 LNS 1895 and *PP v Kelvin Tong Teng Hoe* [2021] 1 LNS 719. Per Mohamed Azmi SCJ in *Junaidi Bin Abdullah v PP* [1993] 3 MLJ 217 states "The test to be applied for the purpose of s 45 of the Evidence Act 1950 is this. First, does the nature of the evidence require special skill? Second, if so, has the witness acquired the necessary skill either by academic qualification or experience so that he has adequate knowledge to express an opinion on the matter under enquiry? The answer to both questions must necessarily depend on the facts of each particular case". At the end of the day, evidence evidences tendered to the court must be relevant and legally admissible and this includes forensic science evidence and testimony given by an expert witness or forensic scientist. This has been heavily stated under Section 5, 136 and 165 of the Evidence Act 1950 [Act 56]. Bear in mind, without the authentication process any evidence including forensic science evidence, such evidence cannot be accepted by the court of law. Such evidence will become hearsay evidence, irrelevant, legally inadmissible and to be rejected.

4.0 CONCLUSION

Forensic science education and law of evidence subject are interconnected to each other. Forensic science strengthens the law of evidence subject. As such, it is vital for forensic science education to be inserted into the law of evidence subject and to be teach to the law students. Due to its complexity and changes nature, forensic science will be developed from time to time. New technology will be created to make forensic science becoming more effective and efficient. Educator and instructor of law of evidence subject need to be aware over new development to the in area of forensic science. Active engagement need to be carry out with the relevant enforcement agencies in order to understand over all the changes made over forensic science matter. Development of Artificial Intelligence (AI) also impact forensic science discussion. Artificial intelligence (AI) refers to computer systems capable of performing complex tasks that historically only a human could do, such as reasoning, making decisions, or solving problems (Russell, Stuart J.; Norvig, Peter., 2021 and Rich, Elaine; Knight, Kevin; Nair, Shivashankar B., 2010).). Today, the term "AI" describes a wide range of technologies that power many of the services and goods we use every day (Coursera Staff, 2024). Artificial Intelligence (AI) and forensic science collaborate to revolutionist crime investigation and evidence analysis, enhancing accuracy and efficiency. The integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) has become more prevalent in various areas, revolutionizing medical and forensic science and solving many complex problems. This is possible due to the recent updates in computer science and technology. Forensic science has embraced Artificial Intelligence (AI) augmenting investigation techniques and contributing to more effective judicial proceeding in both civil and criminal cases (Vineeta Johri, 2024). Due to this reason, it would be wise for law of evidence subject be prepared according to the new development over Artificial Intelligence (AI) and forensic science. This will be the future of our legal education.

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